

CHESS SETUP: STEP 1

Welcome to our 1st newsletter, we wish you a pleasant reading

You will receive this newsletter every 6 months. We will inform you about the project's achievements, and relevant news related to the Energy ecosystem.

The European project investigating buildings' energy self-sufficiency

Funded by the European Commission

CHESS SETUP (680556) contributes to the triple facet of the 2020 Program aiming to cut Greenhouse Gas emissions by 20%, improve energy efficiency by 20% and increase the share of renewable sources by 20%.

The Project

Chess Setup is an implementation project combining various technologies: energy storage, heat pumps, hybrid solar panels, monitorization systems, and smart grids.

Main objective: supplying the most part of buildings' heating and hot water consumption needs from this system working on a seasonal mode. The implementation will be carried out in Catalonia and in England.

What would your system look like ?

The optimal technology combination relies on each of the elements' sizing, but also on some external variables such as the geographical location. Thus, Chess Setup developed a public simulation software available [here](#).

Smart City Expo World Congress

Chess Setup was introduced on big screen during this major event gathering more than 16,000 professionals. Some of the project members attended the presentation and were able to share opinions and experiences among themselves.

Project's progress

Chess Setup was launched 8 months ago, and all Work Packages have already begun their activities. All deliverables were sent on time, and some objectives were already achieved.

"So the challenge for Government and regulators is to design a system that can both better manage intermittency and take advantages of the innovations in storage, demand-side response, interconnection and IT to create a truly smart energy system."

UK Secretary of State for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy; Energy UK Conference; November 11th, 2016

COP 22: an optimistic step towards Paris Agreement's implementation

The time has come to find solution to keep global warming below a 1.5°C increase. In Marrakech, the initiative also came from the 47 poorest countries: they decided to reach a 100% renewable energies goal "as rapidly as possible".

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<http://www.chess-setup.net>

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